
WILLIAM SHAKESPEARE
(APRIL 23, 1564 - APRIL 23, 1616)

Allamurotov Sherzod Jalilovich

teacher of English at School No. 56 in Sherabad District Surkhandarya Region

Annotation: Information about the life and work of William Shakespeare. The importance of his works and tragedies today.

Key words: Tragedy, actor, career, dramatist, master of words, author of English times.

Shakespeare is an English playwright, poet and actor, one of the most famous playwrights in the world. He is the author of 17 comedies, 10 chronicles, 11 tragedies, 5 poems and 154 sonnets. Around 1585, he left his native Stratford-upon-Avon and later went to London. His career as a theater actor and dramatist began in 1580. Shakespeare's acting career lasts about 15 years. Shakespeare played supporting roles in England's best-regarded troupe and wrote plays for that troupe. William Shakespeare's works are a treasure for world literature; this man was an English poet, dramatist and stage actor who lived between the 16th and 17th centuries. However, the cultural impact of his works has transcended centuries. Today it is a symbol of Western art, letters and popular culture. He is considered by some to be the most important author of all time in the English language. Shakespeare's plays cover comedy, historical dramas cover tragedy. These are part of the Elizabethan theatrical tradition, but stand out in quality and importance among other authors. His greatness lies in the fluent use of language, as well as the sharpness, roughness and universality of the images he creates.

William Shakespeare is the 3rd largest writer in the world using more than 20,000 words in his works. William Shakespeare is considered one of the greatest English playwrights. It is difficult to find another person in the world whose life is surrounded by so many assumptions and assumptions. His main gift for drama is real talent.

Facts about William Shakespeare:

1. The great playwright William Shakespeare always lived with secrets.
2. Shakespeare's biographical evidence shows that he was the second most quoted author in the world.

It was Shakespeare who introduced the word "murder" into the everyday life of all people.

4. William Shakespeare did not study at the university.

5. As the facts of Shakespeare's life say, he quickly became famous all over the world.

6. Shakespeare is the greatest artist today.

7. The works of the great playwright that have survived to this day include a collection of 38 plays.

8. Many of Shakespeare's works have been translated into other languages of the world.

9. Performances of this figure are shown in theaters more often than other characters.

10. William Shakespeare began his career as an actor.

11. The great playwright never published his works.

12. Shakespeare had 3 children.

13. According to Shakespeare, his works should only be performed on the stage.

14. About 3000 new words were created by Shakespeare.

15. The play "Macbeth" written by Shakespeare is considered the most famous in the world.

16. There are 2035 words in Shakespeare's works.

17. William Shakespeare painted self-portraits.

18. Shakespeare created 10 tragedies.

19. In 1955, Shakespeare opened a theater.

20. There were no prizes in Shakespeare. It is difficult to imagine the history of world art without Shakespeare. His influence on the development of theater art is immeasurable. His tragedies are among the masterpieces of world literature. Shakespeare's works are not leaving the world stage even today. Despite all his work and fame, William Shakespeare was not awarded any awards or diplomas...

During his creative career, the great playwright created 17 comedies, 11 tragedies, 5 poems, 154 sonnets and 10 chronicles. His poems have been translated into many languages of the world. However, 400 years after Shakespeare's death, the debate about his famous works still continues. At the age of 18, Shakespeare married Anne Hathaway, 8 years his senior, and as a result of this union, three children - Susan and twins Hamnet and Judith - were born. After moving to London, Shakespeare began to create and soon became a successful actor, playwright and founded a theater called "Lord Chamberlain's Servants". At the age of 49, the poet returned to his native Stratford and died there in 1616. On the occasion of the 400th anniversary of Shakespeare's death, we bring to your attention his wisest words.

1. You can fall in love with beauty, but only the soul is loved. 2. Look at yourself before you find fault with others. 3. If we are seriously upset for some reason, we get nervous about trivial things. 4. Evil does not lead to good. 5. Every thoughtless action has its own logic. 6. Oaths taken in a storm are forgotten in calm

air. 7. Men who are looking for a way to their hearts are like April, and married people are like December. 8. I have forgiven the feelings I once felt, and you too - forgive the world -If you want to walk uphill, you should walk slowly first. - A poor contented person is rich, rich enough. He who swims in riches and fears to lose them, is poorer than winter. -Cowards die hundreds of times before they die. A brave man does not taste death but once in his life. - It's easier to get what you want with a smile than with a sword. - A wise man does not sit down to mourn, but begins with joy the task of repairing the damage done. -First of all, your existence must be real. -True hope is swift and flies on the wings of a swallow. "Hidden sorrow, like a closed hearth, turns the heart into mere ashes." -If your friends and you have already tested their friendship, keep them close to your heart with iron hooks. If music is the food of love, let it continue to sing.

William Shakespeare, one of the brightest representatives of world literature, Shakespeare's works are loved and read by readers all over the world to this day. The reason is that the author has created his works with such high skill that he can attract the attention of the reader, using the various possibilities of the artistic genre. A number of his works have been translated into Uzbek and are being performed on theater stages. The most popular of these works is the tragedy "Hamlet".

References:

1. William Shakespeare. Othello. Translated from English by Jamal Kamal. - Tashkent: Literary and art publishing house named after Gafur Ghulam. 1991
2. William Shakespeare. Hamlet. Translated from Russian by Maqsud Sheikhzadeh. Tashkent: Baktriya Press Publishing House, 2013.
3. William Shakespeare. Don't be elected. The first volume. Translated from English by Jamal Kamal. - Tashkent: Science, 2007.